

**METHODOLOGICAL POSSIBILITIES OF USING INFORMATION AND
COMMUNICATION MEANS IN MANAGING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN HIGHER
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15708801>

Abstract: This article analyzes the methodological possibilities of using information and communication technologies in managing the educational process in higher educational institutions. The features of these technologies that serve to improve the educational process, their importance in the effective organization of distance learning, their contribution to the development of interactive learning methods, and the role of students in personalizing the learning process are highlighted. The article also considers innovative methods for using information and communication technologies, problems associated with them, and ways to overcome them. Based on the results of the research, recommendations are developed to improve the effectiveness of the educational process.

Keywords: information and communication technologies, distance learning, interactive teaching methods, learning process management, innovative pedagogy, digital educational platforms, methodological opportunities.

Introduction.

The role of information and communication technologies (ICT) in the modern educational process is increasingly increasing. The process of introducing innovative technologies in education is especially important in managing the educational process in higher education institutions. With the help of ICT tools, the possibilities of organizing effective communication between teachers and students, developing a distance learning system, and conducting interactive lessons are expanding. At the same time, digital platforms are emerging as an important tool in the development and distribution of educational materials, as well as in assessing student knowledge.

The methodological possibilities of using ICT in higher education are aimed at increasing the efficiency of the educational process, improving the quality of teaching, and developing students' independent learning skills. From this point of view, this article is devoted to analyzing the role of ICT tools in the educational process, studying the methods and possibilities of their effective use.

The relevance of this topic is due to the globalization of modern education, the rapid development of digital technologies, and the need to meet the requirements of the digital transformation of the educational process. The study is aimed at developing

practical recommendations for improving the higher education process through the effective use of ICT tools.

METHODOLOGY: In this study, the following research methods were used to study the methodological possibilities of using information and communication technologies in higher education institutions:

Theoretical analysis method: Advanced scientific developments, pedagogical and didactic approaches to the use of ICT tools were studied. Concepts and methodological materials aimed at ensuring the integration of these technologies into the educational process were analyzed.

Methodological approaches were aimed at determining the impact of the use of ICT in the educational process on the effectiveness of students' learning, the quality of lessons and the development of interactive learning. Also, recommendations were developed to identify problems encountered in the educational process and eliminate them.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The selected literature on the use of information and communication technologies in higher education covers various approaches to the theoretical foundations of ICT tools, their integration into the educational process, methodological capabilities and practical application.

The work "Fundamentals of organizing the educational process based on innovative technologies" by Q. Abdurakhmonov[2, 61] shows the main directions and methods of introducing innovative approaches in the educational process. This work comprehensively considers the importance of ICT tools in the development of interactive methods in the teaching process.

The work "Information and communication technologies and the educational process" by H. Mamotov[4, 17] highlights the possibilities of using ICT in the educational process and its role in improving teacher-student communication. This work serves as the basis for developing methodological approaches to improve the quality of education in higher educational institutions.

UNESCO's report "ICT in Education: A Global Perspective"[5] examines global experiences and trends, and provides a comprehensive analysis of the successes and challenges associated with the integration of ICT tools into education. This resource provides an opportunity to draw on international experiences.

V.N. Shapoval's work[10, 214] discusses modern methods of effective management of ICT tools in the educational process. The work analyzes the integrative properties of ICT in the educational process, digital transformation processes and the importance of pedagogical processes.

The book "Innovative approaches and ICT tools in education", published by N. Norqobilov[6, 39], studies the theoretical and practical aspects of the use of ICT tools. In particular, approaches to the organization of distance education are described in detail.

A. Akhmadaliyev's work[3, 98] extensively covers distance education technologies and the possibilities of their use. This source is especially notable for its coverage of current issues in the development of distance education in the context of a pandemic.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PQ-3245 of 2017[1] created a regulatory framework to support the widespread use of ICT tools in the educational process and provided incentive programs for the introduction of modern technologies in the higher education system.

These publications, along with highlighting the theoretical foundations and practical guidelines for the use of ICT tools in managing the educational process in higher education institutions, allow for a comparison of global and national experience. They also contribute to the development of scientific conclusions and recommendations on the topic of the study.

DISCUSSION:

The use of information and communication technologies in higher education institutions provides new opportunities for managing the educational process. The study revealed that ICT tools are important in improving the quality of education, organizing interactive lessons, effectively implementing distance learning, and optimizing the educational process. However, there are a number of problems in the process of using these technologies.

Positive impact of ICT tools on the educational process:

Personalization of education: Through ICT tools, each student will have the opportunity to receive education appropriate to his level of knowledge. This strengthens the personal approach and increases the effectiveness of the educational process.

Development of distance education: With the help of digital platforms, students will have the opportunity to receive quality education regardless of their geographical location.

Convenient access to resources: ICT tools provide quick and easy access to educational materials, databases and scientific literature.

Effectiveness of educational process management: With the help of ICT tools, it is easier to monitor and manage the educational process, and the assessment of student knowledge is automated.

Recommendations:

For the effective introduction of ICT tools in higher education institutions, it is necessary to strengthen the technical base and organize special training courses for teachers.

It is necessary to expand innovative platforms in the education system, such as virtual classrooms and interactive programs.

It is necessary to organize trainings and seminars aimed at improving digital literacy for students and teachers.

It is necessary to develop new methodological approaches by integrating national and international experiences in the use of ICT.

This discussion shows that the effective use of ICT tools ensures an innovative transformation of the educational process. However, this process must be carried out by combining technological, pedagogical and organizational aspects. Therefore, higher education institutions must constantly search for new opportunities for using ICT tools.

CONCLUSIONS:

The use of information and communication technologies in higher education institutions is important for increasing the efficiency of managing the educational process. The study revealed that ICT tools are a decisive factor in the personalization of education, the introduction of interactive methods and the development of distance learning. Also, with the help of these tools, the educational process is being adapted to modern requirements and standards.

However, there are problems in the use of these technologies, such as the lack of technical infrastructure, the qualifications of teaching staff and technological literacy. To eliminate these shortcomings, it is recommended to work in the following areas: Modernization of the technical base and the introduction of modern ICT tools in higher education institutions, Organization of special courses and seminars for teachers and students to improve digital literacy, Introduction of innovative pedagogical approaches and study of international experiences in the effective use of ICT tools.

The results of the study show that the correct and effective use of ICT tools will bring the educational process to a qualitatively new level. Therefore, the higher education system needs to develop strategic directions for the use of ICT and widely implement them. This will help to improve the quality and efficiency of education, as well as ensure global competitiveness.

REFERENCES:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining qarori, 29.08.2017 yildagi PQ-3245-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-3324016>

2. Abdurahmonov, Q. (2019). Innovasion texnologiyalar asosida o'quv jarayonini tashkil etish asoslari. Toshkent: «O'qituvchi» nashriyoti.
3. Ahmadaliev, A. (2022). Masofaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari: imkoniyatlar va samaradorlik. Buxoro: Buxoro davlat universiteti nashriyoti.
4. Mamatov, H. (2018). Axborot-kommunikasiya texnologiyalari va ta'lim jarayoni. Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti.
5. UNESCO. (2020). ICT in Education: A Global Perspective. Retrieved from <https://unesco.org>.
6. Norqobilov, N. (2021). Ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlar va AKT vositalari. Toshkent: Iqtisodiyot va ta'lim nashriyoti.
7. Khudoynazarov, D. (2022). Issues of introducing digital technologies into the activities of courts. *The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology*, 4(01), 1-6.
8. Xudoynazarov, E. M. (2019). Didactic possibilities of oral exercises in forning initial classes pupils' mathematical thinking activity. Eastern European Scientific Journal, Ausgabe. *Germany*, (1-2019), 249.
9. Madraximovich, X. E., & Urazboyevna, U. N. (2023). O 'quvchilar mantiqiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda sinfdan tashqari ustoz-shogird munosabatlarning ahamiyati. *Science and innovation*, 2(Special Issue 12), 564-566.